

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The effect of workload and organizational culture on the performance of civil servants: The role of job satisfaction as a mediator at the DIY DPRD Secretariat

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the effect of workload and organizational culture with job satisfaction as a mediating variable on the performance of civil servants at the Secretariat of the Regional House of Representatives of Yogyakarta Special Region Province. The research sample used the saturated sampling technique method with a total of 55 civil servant respondents. Research data were obtained through direct distribution of questionnaires. The research data were statistically tested through Smart PLS with a P-Value criterion ≤ 0.05 . The results showed that workload has a negative and significant impact on employee performance. While organizational culture has a positive and significant impact on employee performance. In mediation, it is proven that job satisfaction is able to mediate the relationship between workload and employee performance and organizational culture and employee performance.

Keywords: Workload; Organizational Culture; Job Satisfaction; Employee Performance.

1. Introduction

Employee performance is one of the important factors that continues to receive serious attention in the fields of organizational psychology and human resource management ¹. Job performance refers to the actions, behaviors, and scalable results that employees engage in or produce to contribute to goals. This performance concept explicitly describes goal-oriented behavior, namely behavior that is employed by the organization to perform good work results.

Problems regarding employee performance occur in the Secretariat of the Dewan Perwakilan Rakyat Daerah (DPRD) of Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta (DIY). The duties of the DIY DPRD Secretariat are regulated in DIY Governor Regulation No. 132 of 2021 concerning Position, Organizational Structure, Duties, Functions, and Work Procedures of the Secretariat of the Regional People's Representative Council. The position of the DIY DPRD Secretariat is listed in Article 2 paragraph 1 which states that the DPRD Secretariat is an element of administrative services and providing support for the duties and functions of the DPRD.

Based on the results of observations made, it shows that the performance of employees of the DIY DPRD Secretariat in terms of work quality, there are several employees who are unable to complete each job in accordance with the quality standards determined by this organization, the quality of work results tends to be the same and does not improve from time to time, some employees are less able to do work with their creativity and less able to innovate to complete work effectively.

Problems faced in terms of workload include: workload, among others, namely: board members in giving assignments, especially in making work reports and accountability letters, are not in accordance with the specified schedule and the budget that has been set. So that it has an impact on the high stress and fatigue experienced by employees. In addition,

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each employee feels a high workload, especially on the targets that must be achieved. The targets that must be achieved by employees include administration and accountability, but the reality often exceeds the time limit because the parties involved in the field are often late in submitting SPJ files to employees assigned to assist so that the target in the form of budget realization cannot be disbursed and has an impact on low budget absorption which is not on target. Problems related to organizational culture include: 1) Weak innovation in most personnel; 2) Low courage in taking risks; 3) Orientation on results that should be on outcomes, but most are still on output only; 4) Leaders tend to favor some people in assignments; 5) Low consistency in budgeting and implementation of activities.

Job satisfaction at the DIY DPRD Secretariat is perceived by most employees to be low, especially in promotion satisfaction, in this case the opportunity for employees to improve their careers due to the level of echelon 4 which has experienced equalization of Certain Functional Positions (JFT) so that it has an impact on the absence of promotions from implementers to echelon 4 and higher echelon structural positions. Providing work in a short time and dynamically by board members can cause workload for employees. The results of previous studies prove that when workload increases, employees cannot meet some of the expected needs despite the efforts they make, where employees do not have a positive attitude towards their job satisfaction which causes work performance to decrease further ². Employees will do their work in a hurry and difficult to schedule properly which makes the energy expended increase, so that the work results are less optimal.

Employees often work beyond their working hours, which results in a lack of rest and time to spend with their families at home, leading to declining health conditions. Coupled with a weak organizational culture, such as a less conducive work environment and difficulty in adopting new technology, it becomes a major problem in the institution. A poor working environment can result in less harmonious cooperation between employees and superiors, making it difficult to achieve work targets. Meanwhile, the difficulty in adopting information technology systems can hinder employee work, so that work results become less optimal.

For government organizations, employees play an important role in the progress of the organization and are highly dependent on employee performance. Organizations usually have targets that must be completed by employees in carrying out their work as a way to measure their performance. Employee performance can be seen from the results of the assessment conducted by the organization on each employee ³. Employees who are able to carry out their duties and responsibilities well usually have good performance. Conversely, employees who perform poorly usually cannot carry out their work as expected by the organization. Therefore, employee performance is an important factor for organizational progress. Many factors affect employee performance, including workload and organizational culture.

Workload refers to the volume, speed and difficulty of work. The provision of excessive tasks and responsibilities and a short time with a limited number of employees. This condition will lead to high workload. Employees must extend more effort or spend more time to complete their tasks, they may contribute to a higher workload ⁴. Employees will work in a hurry to meet the high load so that the work done is less than optimal. This condition will result in decreased employee performance ⁵. Previous findings show that workload can reduce employee performance ^{6,7}. However, contrary to other studies which have proven that workload can improve employee performance ⁸, while Johari et al. (2018) found that workload actually had no significant effect on employee performance ¹.

Organizational culture plays an important role in government organizations, because organizational culture provides a framework that relates to employee behavior and work climate ⁹. Organizational culture is a system of meanings, values and beliefs in an organization that serves as a reference for action and distinguishes one organization from another it becomes the identity or main characteristic of the organization ¹⁰. The ability of culture to influence employee behavior plays an important role in the organization ¹¹. Organizational culture acts as a catalyst in improving employee performance because it must be an obligation for all members which will create consistency among organizational members ¹². A strong culture is a useful instrument for directing behavior because it helps employees to have higher work performance. Previous findings prove that organizational culture statistically affects employee performance ^{10,13,14}. In contrast to the findings by Pawirosumarto et al. (2017) that organizational culture has no significant effect on employee performance ¹⁶.

The results of research on the relationship between workload and organizational culture on employee performance are still inconsistent with the results of research and need to be strengthened again to be proven empirically. We suspect that satisfaction is a connecting factor to strengthen the relationship between workload and organizational culture with employee performance. Job satisfaction is an employee's emotional attitude or feeling towards work that is pleasant or unpleasant according to the employee's assessment ¹⁷. Job satisfaction is entirely personal, meaning that each individual has their own characteristics and perspectives, including opinions. Employee job satisfaction will decrease if there is

unpleasant work that can drain employee energy and time including time to gather with family which forces them to extend working time. This results in a higher workload so that their performance decreases. Previous findings prove that higher workload can reduce job satisfaction which can then reduce employee performance^{17,18}. However, in contrast to the results of other studies that job satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between workload and employee performance^{5,8}.

Job satisfaction needs to be considered because it is a criterion for measuring the success of a company by employees. A person's job satisfaction can increase if they have a conducive climate that makes them comfortable and can indirectly encourage them to work optimally. The results of previous research prove that job satisfaction can significantly mediate between organizational culture and employee performance^{9,19}. These results contradict previous findings that job satisfaction cannot mediate the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance^{20,15}. The issue of workload and organizational culture is a central issue because it will affect the job satisfaction of employee performance at the DIY Provincial DPRD Secretariat to decrease. In addition, there are still inconsistencies in the results of research related to the impact of workload and organizational culture on employee performance mediated by job satisfaction, so it is necessary to test again.

Figure 1 Framework Model

2. Methods

This type of causality research looks at the relationship between two or more research variables. The population in this study were all civil servants of the DIY Regional Government DPRD Secretariat, totaling 55 civil servants. This study took a population sample. To produce more effective and efficient research and produce unbiased results, sampling was carried out. This study uses a saturated sampling technique, which means that each population is considered as a sample²¹. The sample in this study is all civil servants totaling 55 employees because:

- a. In accordance with Article 1 of the Regulation of the Minister of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Number 6 of 2022 states "State Civil Apparatus Employees, hereinafter referred to as Employees, are civil servants and government employees with work agreements who are appointed by civil service officials and assigned duties in a government position or assigned other state duties and paid based on statutory regulations".
- b. Non-civil servants (auxiliary staff and outsourcing) do not fill in the Performance Appraisal System.

Data was collected using a two-part questionnaire. The first section collected respondents' demographic information, such as gender, age, education, and length of service. The second part included research indicators for each variable tested. At the DIY Provincial DPRD Secretariat Office, researchers directly distributed questionnaires to respondents. Data analysis uses Smart PLS which is tested in three stages. First, test the outer model with three methods used to measure the feasibility of the instrument. The criteria used to assess convergent validity with a loading factor ≥ 0.50 , composite reliability with Cronbach Alpha ≥ 0.60 or $\rho_c \geq 0.70$, and discriminant validity with AVE ≥ 0.50 . Second, test the inner model by testing R Square, Q Square, and Goodness of Fit. Finally, test the hypothesis with the criteria P-Value ≤ 0.05 .

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Description of Respondents

This research was conducted on 55 civil servants of the DIY Provincial DPRD Secretariat. Researchers obtained data through direct distribution of questionnaires to 55 respondents. To find out the characteristics of respondents, descriptive statistical tests were carried out. This test was conducted to determine gender; age; education; and length of service. The findings showed that most respondents were male as many as 29 respondents (52.7%). The age of respondents is mostly between 18 years to 30 years as many as 30 respondents (54.5%) with the most education is Bachelor as many as 29 respondents (52.7%), and working for 1 year to 5 years as many as 27 respondents (49.1%).

Table 1 Characteristics of Respondents (N=55)

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	29	52.7
	Female	26	47.3
Age	18-30 years	30	54.5
	31-40 years	16	29.1
	41-50 years	4	7.3
	>50 years	5	9.1
Education	Senior High School	7	12.7
	Diploma	14	25.5
	Bachelor	29	52.7
	Master	5	9.1
Length of Service	<1 years	7	12.7
	1-5 years	27	49.1
	6-10 years	11	20.0
	11-15 years	2	3.6
	>15 years	8	14.5
Total		55	100,0

3.2. Outer Model Test Results

The outer model test this time is by eliminating items B01; B03; B04; B05; B06; and B010 (organizational culture variable) and items KP3; and KP4 (job satisfaction variable) because they have a loading factor value 0.50, so the research data is declared to meet the convergent validity criteria. The composite reliability test results have a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.60 and $\rho_c > 0.70$, meaning that the research data meets the composite reliability criteria. The discriminant validity test results have an AVE value > 0.50 , so it is in accordance with the discriminant validity criteria. Therefore, the research data has met the instrument criteria, so it is suitable for further testing. The following is a summary of the final data instrument test results.

Table 2 Instrument Test Results

Variable	Item	Loading Factor	Cronbach Alpha	ρ c	AVE	Results
Workload	BK1	0.590	0.878	0.902	0.509	Valid & Reliable
	BK2	0.814				
	BK3	0.787				
	BK4	0.755				
	BK5	0.729				
	BK6	0.573				
	BK7	0.686				
	BK8	0.761				
	BK9	0.688				
Organizational Culture	B02	0.524	0.879	0.905	0.547	Valid & Reliable
	B07	0.722				
	B08	0.773				
	B09	0.663				
	B011	0.745				
	B012	0.767				
	B013	0.815				
	B014	0.859				
Job Satisfaction	KP1	0.613	0.884	0.911	0.567	Valid & Reliable
	KP2	0.664				
	KP5	0.860				
	KP6	0.824				
	KP7	0.873				
	KP8	0.894				
	KP9	0.629				
	KP10	0.588				
Employee Performance	KN1	0.640	0.957	0.961	0.517	Valid & Reliable
	KN2	0.726				
	KN3	0.563				
	KN4	0.756				
	KN5	0.630				
	KN6	0.628				
	KN7	0.609				
	KN8	0.705				
	KN9	0.816				
	KN10	0.844				

	KN11	0.848				
	KN12	0.698				
	KN13	0.777				
	KN14	0.736				
	KN15	0.798				
	KN16	0.778				
	KN17	0.662				
	KN18	0.686				
	KN19	0.782				
	KN20	0.788				
	KN21	0.625				
	KN22	0.681				
	KN23	0.662				

3.3. Inner Model Test Results

Inner model test to determine whether the research model is in accordance with the structural model tested by conducting three tests, namely: R Square, Q Square, and Goodness of Fit (GoF). The results of the structural model feasibility test with the inner model approach through the R Square method show that on average it has an R2 value of 0.560 or in the moderate category. The Q Square test results have a Q2 value of 0.272 or considered moderate. While the GoF test results show that it has a GoF value of 0.541 so that the research model has a strong structural model feasibility, so it is feasible to test the hypothesis.

Table 3 Inner Model Test Results

Model	R ²	Q ²	GoF
Job Satisfaction	0.373	0.177	0.449
Employee Performance	0.746	0.367	0.632
Average	0.560	0.272	0.541

3.4. Hypothesis Test Results

Table 4 Hypothesis Test Results

Influence between Variables	β	T Stat	P Values
Workload -> Employee Performance	-0.390	4.308	0.000**
Workload -> Job Satisfaction	-0.297	2.524	0.012*
Organizational Culture -> Employee Performance	0.272	3.022	0.003**
Organizational Culture -> Job Satisfaction	0.406	3.481	0.001**
Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0.386	3.494	0.001**
Workload -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	-0.114	2.231	0.026*
Organizational Culture -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0.157	2.438	0.015*

Notes: ** significant at α 0,01 (1%) (two tailed); * significant at α 0,05 (5%) (two tailed).

Hypothesis testing in this study uses path analysis which is tested through Smart PLS with seven hypotheses proposed. The assessment criteria are the P-value \leq 0.05, then the hypothesis is accepted. Table 4 shows that the effect of workload

on employee performance ($\beta=-0.390$, $P<0.01$); workload on job satisfaction ($\beta=-0.297$, $P<0.05$), so H1 and H2 are accepted. The influence of organizational culture on employee performance ($\beta=0.272$, $P<0.01$); organizational culture on job satisfaction ($\beta=0.406$, $P<0.01$), so that H3 and H4 are accepted. Meanwhile, the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance ($\beta=0.386$, $P<0.01$), which means that H5 is accepted. By mediation, we found that job satisfaction mediates the effect of workload on employee performance ($\beta=-0.114$, $P<0.05$); and the influence of organizational culture on employee performance ($\beta=0.157$, $P<0.05$) which means that H6 and H7 are accepted.

4. Discussion

This study investigates the effect of workload and organizational culture on the performance of civil servants of the DIY Provincial DPRD Secretariat. The results showed that higher workload can reduce job satisfaction and employee performance. Employees feel overwhelmed by a high volume of tasks or tight deadlines, their ability to concentrate, make decisions, and complete tasks effectively may be compromised. They attempt to complete more tasks under heavy workloads to the point of being unable to devote sufficient time and attention to each task, leading to a decline in the quality of their work. This can lead to decreased productivity and low-quality work outcomes¹⁸. Decreased productivity and quality of work resulting from high workload can affect job satisfaction and lower employee performance^{7,17,18}.

We also found that organizational culture can significantly improve job satisfaction and employee performance. Employees feel a strong alignment between their personal values and the values embedded in the organizational culture. A culture that emphasizes teamwork, collaboration, open communication, and mutual support fosters a sense of belonging, encourages employee development, and promotes a positive work environment. This alignment contributes to a positive work environment and, in turn, a positive organizational culture can increase employee job satisfaction and performance^{9,14,22}. In addition, we found that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance. Employees who have high satisfaction have good performance¹⁴. In this case, employees are satisfied with their job, salary, promotion, supervision and coworkers which encourage their performance to improve.

5. Conclusion

We conducted research on the performance of civil servants at the Secretariat of the DPRD of Yogyakarta Province. The results showed that workload has a significant effect on employee satisfaction and performance. We also found that a positive organizational culture can significantly improve employee satisfaction and performance. In this study, job satisfaction can also affect employee performance. This means that employees who have high satisfaction can improve their performance. Meanwhile, mediation shows that job satisfaction is able to mediate the influence between workload and organizational culture on employee performance.

The DIY Provincial DPRD Secretariat has two types of employees, namely civil servants and non-civil servants. However, this research is more focused on civil servants, which is a limitation of the research, while non-civil servants have a high workload. Therefore, further research is not only on civil servants who are the research sample but also on non-civil servants to find out perspectives on workload, organizational culture, job satisfaction, and employee performance as a whole.

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